

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

Datasets and compression methods contained in Jupyter notebooks are available online to allow for compression evaluations

Milestone M3.3

ESiWACE3 Milestone M3.3

EuroHPC
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1. Abstract / publishable summary

This milestone documents the publication of an Online Laboratory for Data Compression in Climate Science and Meteorology that allows the testing of various compression methods for output of both weather and climate models. The Jupyter notebooks of the compression laboratory explore several datasets for ensemble weather predictions and climate simulations, apply lossy compression techniques in an easy-to-use way, and allow to perform a number of diagnostics to evaluate possible degradations due to compression. We also provide an online laboratory as a service, which hosts the compression laboratory notebooks and allows users to quickly jump in and explore compression without needing to install or setup anything. A detailed description of the data and tools can be found in deliverable D3.3 that is published alongside this milestone document.

Based on the developments of this milestone M3.3 and deliverable D3.3, the team working on the compression task will organise community outreach, including a hackathon, to explore compression techniques in detail over the next two years, and explore and document potential trade-offs between a reduction of the data that need to be stored, the computational cost to compress and de-compress the data, and the compression error that will impact diagnostics performed on top of the stored data.

2. Conclusion and Results

The compression laboratory, which consists of several Jupyter notebooks exploring data compression, has been published. Version 0.2 of the notebooks can be accessed at <https://github.com/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks/releases/tag/v0.2> on GitHub, [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14526226](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14526226) on Zenodo, and <https://compression.lab.climet.eu/v0.2> in the online laboratory. The notebooks are published under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

We provide an online laboratory for climate science and meteorology, which resembles a JupyterLab deployment but runs server-less in the user's own web browser and comes with important weather and climate Python packages pre-installed. Version 0.2 of the online laboratory can be accessed at <https://lab.climet.eu/v0.2> and its source code is published at <https://github.com/climet-eu/lab/releases/tag/v0.2> on GitHub. The online laboratory is published under the Mozilla Public License 2.0.

In combination, the online compression laboratory (the compression laboratory hosted in the online laboratory) provides a quick, installation- and setup-free way to test out data compression on weather and climate datasets by visiting <https://compression.lab.climet.eu>.

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Figure 1: Screenshot of the compression laboratory when it is launched inside the online laboratory

We are now ready to perform a more detailed evaluation of lossy compression for weather and climate data in the next two years, and to use the published datasets and compression laboratory as the basis of our community outreach including a hackathon.

3. References

This milestone report only provides a very brief overview of the achieved results. Please refer to the deliverable D3.3 report, in particular sections 4.1-4.2 and 4.4-4.5, for a detailed description of the motivation, development, and results of this milestone and how it relates to the broader vision of T3.3.